

Compound **1** was isolated in 1913 and the complete structure was determined in 1940 by Hans Fischer [1-2]. Isolation of chlorophylls from natural sources has been known to be difficult as a result of its various possible decomposition reactions such as demetallation, dephytylation, photooxidation, epimerization, allomerization, solvolysis and demethoxycarbonylation [1]. Chlorophyll *a* **1** and its derivatives are very important model compounds in theoretical chemistry to test the concepts of electron structure, aromaticity, electron transfer, quantum chemistry, coordination and photochemistry. Application of chlorophylls derivatives such as chlorin-*e*₆ **4**, mono L-aspartyl chlorin-*e*₆ **5** and photochlorin **6** (Fig. 2) concerns food chemistry, cosmetic, nanotechnology and treatment of cancer [3-6]. Photodynamic therapy was employed to treat malignant tumors of the skin, mammary gland, mucous membrane of the oral cavity, tongue, lower lip, larynx, lung, esophagus, stomach, urinary bladder and rectum [1-3,7].

Figure 2: Chlorophyll derivatives as possible sensitizer for photodynamic therapy

In our synthetic studies in the field of chlorophyll chemistry, we were interested to develop and improve a partial synthetic pathway methylphephobide **8** and chlorin-*e*₆ trimethylester **10** leading from extracted **1** [1,4,7-8].

Results and Discussion

Semi-quantitative of **1**

HPLC method must be implemented in the special conditions because chlorophylls are very easy decomposed by demetalization, dephytylation, oxidation, allomerization and demethoxycarboxylation but UV-VIS is more convenient method for semi-quantitative of **1**. UV-VIS of **1**, 5.10^{-6} M in acetone, is showed including two main peaks of Soret band at 410nm and Q-band at 667nm. The peak at 667nm ($\epsilon=0,8579.10^5$) was selected to determine the content of **1** by the calibration curve method. The chlorophyll *a* **1** content of bamboo leaves, mulberry leaves, erythrina variegata L, spinat, silkworm waste and spirulina were shown in the **Table 1**.

Table 1: The content of **1** in some sources collected in Vietnam

No	Samples	Chlorophyll (% mass)
1	Erythrina variegata L (at Bac Ninh, Vietnam)	0.028 ± 0.002
2	Bamboo leaves (at Bac Ninh, Vietnam)	0.046 ± 0.005
3	Erythrina orientalis leaves (at Bac Ninh, Vietnam)	0.034 ± 0.001
4	Mulberry leaves (at Bac Ninh, Vietnam)	0.023 ± 0.002
5	Spinat (at Ba Vi, Vietnam)	0.109 ± 0.008
6	Pennisetum purpureum (at Bac Ninh, Vietnam)	0.162 ± 0.002
7	Silkworm waste (at Bac Ninh, Vietnam)	0.265 ± 0.009
8	Spirulina (at Vinh Hao, Vietnam)	0.682 ± 0.013

Chlorophyll contents in some sources are arranged from 0.023-0.682% by mass. Spirulina (0.682%) and silkworm waste (0.265%) are potent of chlorophyll sources.

Extraction of chlorophyll *a* 1 from silkworm waste and directed transformation to methylpheophorbide *a* 8

The extraction of **1** from silkworm waste and transformation to methylpheophorbide *a* were performed by one-pot manner (**Scheme 1**). The mixture of silkworm waste and methanol was stirred with methanol for 2 hours at ambient temperature. The chlorophyll *a* 1 solution was obtained by removal biomass. The transformation **1** to **8** was performed directly without purification by addition of concentrated sulfuric acid with the removal magnesium in the chromophore forming pheophytin *a* intermediate and methyl transesterification. Chlorophyll *b* 2 derivatives impurity was removed by column chromatography on alox. Purification of compound **8** has trouble due to π -stacking interaction of 18 electrons π conjugated and can be solved by recrystallization. Pure **8** is very important intermediate for the preparation of copper chlorophyllin and chlorin-*e*₆ trimethylester. The yield of recovered **8** is higher than 80% from **1** content in the silkworm waste with the mass of 3.85 g from 2 kg silkworm waste.

Scheme 1: Preparation of methylpheophorbide a 8 from silkworm waste

An improved soxhlet extraction of chlorophyll *a* 1 from spirulina and transformation to methylpheophorbide *a* 8.

Spirulina, one kind of cyanobacterium, have only compound **1** and can be considered as the best chlorophyll source. The procedure was performed by soxhlet extraction method with acetone (**Scheme 2**). The transformation crude compound **1** to **8** was performed by a solution of 5% concentrated sulfuric acid in methanol and stirred 24 hours at room temperature, darkness and inert atmosphere. Analytical methylpheophorbide *a* **8** was received by chromatography and recrystallization by $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$. The yield of recovered pheophorbide *a* is higher than 85% from chlorophyll contents in the spirulina with the mass of 2.96 g (0.592%) from 500 g spirulina biomass. Methylpheophorbide *a* has two diastereomers at position of carbon 13² in carbocyclic ring. The ratio between 13^{2R} and 13^{2S} diastereomers is 89/11 which was determined by ¹H-MNR. Hyperchem calculation shows that the energy of *R*-diastereomer is less than 3.15 kcal/mol compare to 13^{2S}-diastereomer.

Scheme 2: Preparation of methylpheophorbide a 8 from spirulina

Preparation of chlorin *e*₆-trimethylester **10**

Chlorin-*e*₆ trimethylester **10** is an intermediate for the synthesis of chlorin-*e*₆ and its derivatives. Compound **10** was conveniently prepared by methanolysis of methylpheophorbide *a* **8** by treatment with 0.5% potassium methanolate in methanol [9] (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3: Methanolysis of methyl pheophorbide *a* **8** to form chlorin *e*₆-trimethylester **10**

Methylpheophorbide *a* **8** and chlorin-*e*₆ trimethylester **10** are poorly soluble in methanol at low temperature. This prevents the homogeneity of the reaction so that a second solvent is necessary to keep the reaction homogeneously. For these purposes, a second solvent is added for instance THF, CH_2Cl_2 or pyridine. During the methanolysis reaction to prevent allomerization, oxygen should be avoided although methanolysis occurs more rapidly than allomerization [7]. Theoretically and practically, the methanolysis reaction cannot proceed completely due to the reverse reaction, therefore the reaction mixture always contains **10** and small amount of **8**. Retention times of methylpheophorbide *a* and chlorin-*e*₆ trimethylester **10** on silicagel or aluminium oxide are quite similar so that they cannot be separated clearly by flash chromatography or HPLC. Isothermic crystallization of compound **10** represents a useful purification procedure. Purity of **10** is more than 99% by HPLC analysis.

Experimental Section

All the chemicals and solvents used for the synthesis work acquired from commercial sources, were of analytical grade, and used without further purification. IR spectra were measured on GX-Perkin Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer. ¹H-NMR spectra were recorded at 500 MHz (Bruker XL-500) with CDCl_3 as solvent and tetramethylsilane as internal standard. Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) were obtained with an Agilent 1100 Series MS mass spectrometer. High resolution electron spray (ES) were obtained with an Agilent technologies 6210 series time of flight. Melting points of crystalline compounds were measured with a Gallenkamp.

Preparation of **8** from silkworm waste

The mixture of 2 kg of silkworm waste and 3 liters of methanol was stirred for 2 hours at ambient temperature. At the end of the extraction the biomass was removed by filtration and washed twice with portions of 200 ml of MeOH. 25 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid was added to the filtrate and the mixture was stirred in the dark under an argon atmosphere for 24 hours. The mixture was added 500 ml of CH_2Cl_2 , 700 ml of H_2O and 300 ml of 10% NaHCO_3 aq. solution. The organic phase was separated, and the water phase was extracted twice with portions of 200 ml of CH_2Cl_2 . The extract was washed with 200ml of water, dried through cotton wood and removed solvent by rotary following by high vacuum to get crude methylpheophorbide *a* in red colour. Analytical methylpheophorbide was received by column chromatography (Alox; CH_2Cl_2 /acetone 15:1) and recrystallization from acetone/ MeOH. The yield of **8** is higher than 80% from chlorophyll content in the silkworm waste with the mass of 3.85 g.

Preparation of **8** from spirulina

The Soxhlet extractor containing 500g of dry spirulina and 5 liters of acetone was heated to reflux in the dark under an argon atmosphere for 2 hours. The extract was removed solvent by rotary and then by high vacuum. The solution

of 25 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄ and 500 ml CH₃OH was added to the dried residual and the mixture was stirred for 24 hours at room temperature, darkness and inert atmosphere. At the end of the reaction, the treatment and purification were performed similar to the silkworm waste procedure. The yield of recovered **8** is higher than 85% from chlorophyll content in the spirulina with the mass of 2.96 g (0.592% of biomass).

R_f: 0.57 (Alox, CH₂Cl₂/ pet/ acetone 10:10:1).

Mp: 226-227°C (CH₂Cl₂/ MeOH, Lit.: 220-225°C, Lit.: 228°C).

IR (KBr): $\tilde{\nu}$ = 3387 cm⁻¹ (w, N-H), 2957 (w), 2865 (w), 1732 (s, C=O, ester), 1700 (s, C=O, ester), 1621 (m, C=C, aromatic), 1557 (w), 1498 (w), 1434 (w), 1366 (w), 1347 (w), 1298 (w), 1203 (s, C-O-C, ester), 1164 (s, br, C-O-C, ester), 1123 (w), 1036 (w), 991 (w), 910 (w), 894 (w), 830 (w), 753 (w), 672 (w).

UV/ VIS (THF): λ_{\max} (ex10⁻³) = 320 (20.63), 410 (106.05), 505 (11.31), 535 (9.95), 610 (7.87), 670 (48.86).

¹H-NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 13²R [13²S] = - 1.61 ppm [- 1.43] (s, br, 1H, NH), 0.54 [0.89] (s, br, 1H, NH), 1.71 (t, ³J = 7.82 Hz, 3H, CH₃, 8²), 1.83 (d, ³J = 7.34 Hz, 3H, CH₃, 18¹), 2.10 - 2.70 (m, 4H, 2CH₂, 17¹ and 17²), [3.21] 3.25 (s, 3H, CH₃, 7¹), [3.39] 3.42 (s, 3H, CH₃, 2¹), [3.54] 3.59 (s, 3H, CH₃, 12¹), 3.70 (q, ³J = 7.82 Hz, 2H, CH₂, 8¹), 3.71 (s, 3H, CH₃, 17⁴), [3.84] 3.89 (s, 3H, CH₃, 13³), 4.05 - 4.25 (m, 1H, CH, 17), 4.48 (q, ³J = 7.34 Hz, 1H, CH, 18), 6.20 (d, ³J = 11.24 Hz, *cis* - vinyl, ³J = 11.24 Hz, =CH₂, 3²), 6.28 (s, 1H, CH, 13²), 6.30 (d, ³J = 17.66 Hz, *trans* - vinyl, 1H, =CH₂, 3²), 8.01 (dd, ³J = 11.24 Hz, *cis* - vinyl, ³J = 17.66 Hz, *trans* - vinyl, 1H, =CH, 3¹), [8.52] 8.59 (s, 1H, meso proton), [9.37] 9.41 (s, 1H, meso proton), [9.51] 9.54 (s, 1H, meso proton). Ratio 13²R/ 13²S = 89:11.

MS: (EI, 70 eV, direct, T = 200 °C): m/z (% rel. intensity) = 606 (100) [M⁺], 548 (29), 459 (17), 236 (10), 44 (40), 28 (100) [C₂H₄]⁺.

MS: (ESI, positive, CH₂Cl₂/MeOH 1:10): 607 [M + H]⁺, 629 [M + Na]⁺, 645 [M + K]⁺.

MS: (ESI, negative, CH₂Cl₂/ MeOH 1:10): 605 [M - H]⁻.

Precision mass: 606.2842 (Cal.).

BRN: 604709.

CAS: 5594-30-9, 64070-09-3, 138812-88-1.

Synthesis of chlorin e₆-trimethylester **10** [9]

1516 mg (2.5 mmol) of **8** was dissolved in 50 ml of dry THF under an argon atmosphere. Thereafter, 200 ml of CH₃OH, 5 ml of a 30-35% solution of potassium methoxide in methanol were added. The mixture was stirred in the dark under an argon atmosphere for 30 minutes. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC (silicagel, CH₂Cl₂/ EtOAc 7:1). At the end of the reaction, 500 ml of H₂O, 10 ml of 2N aq. HCl and 100 ml aq. sat. NaCl were added. The mixture was extracted twice with portions of 100 ml of diethylether. The combined organic phases were washed twice with portions of 200 ml of H₂O and dried by filtration through cotton wool. The solvent was removed by rotary. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silicagel, CH₂Cl₂/ EtOAc 7:1).

Analytically pure **10** was obtained after recrystallization from acetone/ MeOH as lustrous dark blue needles.

Yield: 1350 mg (yield 85 %).

Mp: 208-209°C (acetone/ MeOH, Lit. [9]: 207-208 °C).

R_f: 0.59 (silicagel, CH₂Cl₂/ EtOAc 7:1).

IR (KBr): $\tilde{\nu}$ = 3296 cm⁻¹ (w, N-H), 2954 (m, C=CH), 2914 (w), 2868 (w), 1731 (s, br, C=O, ester), 1601 (m, C=C, aromatic), 1496 (w), 1439 (m), 1370 (w), 1306 (w), 1240 (m, br, C-O-C), 1165 (m), 1118 (w), 1064 (m), 1028 (w), 986 (w), 907 (w), 894 (w), 845 (w), 796 (w), 730 (w), 670 (w).

UV/ VIS (THF): λ_{\max} (ex10⁻³) = 285 (12.59), 305 (10.72), 400 (123.51), 500 (10.86), 530 (4.46), 610 (4.45), 665 (42.44).

¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = - 1.47 ppm (s, br, 1H, NH), - 1.30 (s, br, 1H, NH), 1.73 (t, ³J = 7.34 Hz, 3H, CH₃, 8²), 1.77 (d, ³J = 7.30 Hz, 3H, CH₃, 18¹), 2.18 - 2.22 (m, 4H, 2 CH₂, 17¹ and 17²), 3.31 (s, 3H, CH₃, 7¹), 3.49 (s, 3H, CH₃, 2¹), 3.59 (s, 3H, CH₃, 12¹), 3.78 (s, 3H, CH₃, 17⁴), 3.80 (q, ³J = 7.34 Hz, 2H, CH₂, 8¹), 4.27 (s, 3H, CH₃, 15³), 4.44 (q, ³J = 7.30 Hz, 1H, CH, 18), 5.23 (d, 1H, ²J = 18.58 Hz, CH₂, 15¹), 5.37 (d, 1H, ²J = 18.58 Hz, CH₂, 15¹), 6.16

(d, $^3J = 11.72$ Hz, *cis* - vinyl, 1H, =CH₂, 3²), 6.37 (d, $^3J = 17.60$ Hz, *trans* - vinyl, 1H, =CH₂, 3²), 8.08 (dd, $^3J = 11.72$ Hz, *cis* - vinyl, $^3J = 17.60$ Hz, *trans* - vinyl, 1H, =CH, 3¹), 8.75 (s, 1H, meso proton), 9.58 (s, 1H, meso proton), 9.87 (s, 1H, meso proton), 9.70 (s, 1H, meso proton).

MS: (EI, 70 eV, direct, T = 200 °C): m/z (% rel. intensity) = 638 (100) [M⁺], 579 (13) [M - COOCH₃]⁺, 479 (20), 289 (7), 236 (7), 28 (19) [C₂H₄]⁺.

Precision mass: 638.3104 (Cal.).

BRN: 76355.

CAS: 15592-17-3.

Conclusion

An improved isolation and transformation chlorophyll *a* **1** to methylpheophorbide *a* and chlorin-*e*₆ trimethylester were performed in the safety conditions and can be scaled up to the pilot plant. The yield of recovered pheophorbide *a* **8** is higher than 80% from chlorophyll content. Pure methylpheophorbide *a* and chlorin-*e*₆ trimethylester **10** can be used for food additive or transformed to chlorin-*e*₆ and its derivatives using for photodynamic therapy.

Acknowledgements

The authors are indebted to the Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology for financially supported in part by scientific research and technological development project (code: VAST.ĐT.TP.04/16-18).

References

1. P. H. Hynninen, Chemistry of Chlorophylls: Modification in Chlorophylls, *Chlorophylls*, H. Scheer, Eds., Boca Raton Ann Arbor Boston London, 1, 145-209 (1991).
2. F. P. Montforts, M. G. Breiling, Naturally Occurring Tetrapyrroles: Progress in the Chemistry of Organic Natural Products, Ed, *Springer Wien New York*, 84, 1-51 (2004).
3. W. Schmidt, F.-P. Montforts, Synthesis of a novel enantiomerically pure chlorin as a potential subunit for an artificial, *Synlett*, 903-904, (1997).
4. Webber, B. Leeson, D. Fromm, D. Kessel, Effects of photodynamic therapy using a fractionated dosing of mono-l-aspartyl chlorin *e*₆ in a murine tumor, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. B: Biol.* 78, 135-140, (2005).
5. Y. Amao, T. Komori, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 19, 843-847 (2004).
6. C. L. Bergstrom, I. Vucenic, I. K. Hagen, S. A. Chernomorsky, R. D. Poretz, *J. Photochem. and Photobiol. B: Biol.*, 24, 17-23 (1994).
7. D. Kessel, K. Woodburn, C. J. Gomer, N. Jagerovic, K. M. Smith, Photosensitization with derivatives of chlorin, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. B: Biol.* 28, 13-18, (1995).
8. W. Kühlbrandt, D. N. Wang, Y. Fujiyoshi, Atomic model of plant light-harvesting complex by electron crystallography, *Nature*, 367, 614, (1994).
9. M. Stapelbroek-Möllmann, *Dissertation*, Helsinki/Bremen 1997

